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Famous Charts and Forgotten Fragments: Exploring Correlations in Early Portuguese Nautical Cartography

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Famous Charts and Forgotten Fragments: Exploring Correlations in Early Portuguese Nautical Cartography**

The authors of the well-known collection *Portugaliae Monumenta Cartographica* hinted at connections between two anonymous portolan charts from the beginning of the sixteenth century, namely the portolan chart at the Bibliothèque Municipale of Dijon and a fragment of a chart kept in Lisbon in the Archive at Torre do Tombo. Later, they also mentioned affinities between those two charts and the famous chart known as Kunstmann III. However, they did not pursue these observations further.

The present paper proceeds from where those researchers stopped investigating and proposes a fresh look on this cartographic material by combining a traditional historical approach with modern digital techniques. First, a comparative study of the toponomy of a common area of the charts will be presented. Later, each chart will be examined with the help of cartometric methods to access their implicit geometry. The advancements on the study of correlations between these charts will be shown, thus confirming that the combination of traditional and digital methods of investigation open very promising perspectives to the study of unsolved questions in the History of Cartography.

Keywords: cartometric analysis; portolan charts; Portuguese cartography; 16th century.

The history of cartography is full of problems and questions left unresolved by past researchers: examples of incorrect dates of production, mistaken authors, wrongly identified territories, and suggested affiliations between charts of unknown authors, etc., are not infrequent in this field of knowledge. To ascribe such oversights to intellectual deficiency or defective scholarship is typically unjustified. Many such lapses are the result of a shortage of relevant sources or of limitations inherent in the analytical techniques accessible to previous researchers. Fortunately, the history of cartography is a dynamic and continuously-evolving field. Using new methodologies and approaches, including digital techniques, investigators can now pick up where past scholars left off and successfully address unresolved questions.

The present paper explores connections between three manuscript charts of the sixteenth century, as proposed by previous researchers. The objects under study are: a) a portolan chart

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at the Bibliothèque Municipale of Dijon (hereafter Dijon chart);¹ b) a fragment of a chart in Lisbon, in the Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo (hereafter ANTT fragment);² and c) the chart known as Kunstmann III (hereafter K3).³ The three items in question are anonymous and undated, hence it is difficult to confirm any possible common origin or authorship. The goal of the present paper is to complement the published studies about these charts with new information obtained, on the one hand, via traditional historical approaches (namely the study of toponomy) and, on the other hand, by the use of cartometric analysis.⁴ In particular, the results of the following procedures are presented in this article: 1) a partial comparative analysis of the toponomy of the charts; 2) a comparative cartometric digital analysis of the geometry of the charts, with the assistance of the program MapAnalyst.⁵

The Dijon Portolan Chart

The Dijon chart is an unsigned and undated portolan chart from the early 16th century. The chart was designed on a parchment of about 67x100 cm. It centers on the Mediterranean, like most contemporary portolan charts, and the illustrations and decorations are comparable to those found in Catalan/Majorcan specimens. The wind rose system is constructed around a central compass rose placed above the west coast of Sardinia. The roses are drawn in a “transitional” style (Cortêsão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. VI, p. 85), showing two different designs evident in the illustration of the cardinal direction of the north. Hereafter, I will identify them as type A and type B. Type A shows the fleur-de-lis, a recently adopted decoration that would be the norm for Portuguese cartography during the sixteenth century. Other features are the three scales of leagues, two horizontal and one vertical, and the shape of Scandinavia also following Catalan/Majorcan models (Winter, 1955, p. 49).

It appears that the first researcher to mention this portolan chart was Viscount Santarém. He wrote a brief report on it in 1851 (published 1919), in which he ascribed it to the Catalan/Majorcan school.⁶ Meanwhile, in 1876, Paul Gaffarel presented an extended study with a thorough description of that chart. Based in several arguments, such as the presence of place names written in Italian and considerations about the history of some of the represented cities

¹ Dijon, Bibliothèque Municipale de Dijon, Ms. 550.

² Lisbon, ANTT, Fragmentos, cx. 20, n.º 7.

³ The chart is known as Kunstmann III, or Kunstmann n° 3, due to its sequence in the catalogue (Kunstmann et al., 1859). The original chart was lost during World War II. In 1836, a hand-drawn copy of the complete chart in colour was made by the German artist Otto Progel. This copy was donated to the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Paris) in 1843. See: Département Cartes et Plans, CPL GE B-1120 (RES). There is also a photographic reproduction of the original K3 chart, published in four sheets in (Stevenson, 1903, no. 3) (artotype, four sheets, 1220x830 mm).

⁴ The use of cartometric methods to investigate the geometry of the medieval and early modern cartographic material is one of the goals of the MEDEA-CHART, hosted by the Department of History and Philosophy of Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, University of Lisbon and the Interuniversity Center for the History of Sciences and Technology (CIUHCT). See: [<https://www.medeia-chart.org>].

⁵ MapAnalyst is a freeware computer application developed by Bernhard Jenny and Adrian Weber. Free access online at: <http://mapanalyst.org>.

⁶ (Santarém, 1919, pp. 129-131).

and regions, he supposed that the Dijon chart was produced between 1415 and 1429, by a Genoese author (Gaffarel, 1874, p. 160).

Figure 1 - The anonymous portolan chart known as Dijon Chart. Dijon, Bibliothèque Municipale de Dijon, Ms. 550.

Presently, specialists tend to agree that both Santarém and Gaffarel were inaccurate in their conclusions about the origin and dating of the chart. Santarém's opinion was associated with the decorative elements of the chart, which are very common in Catalan/Majorcan cartography: for example, the tents in North Africa and the style of the drawing of the Red Sea, rivers, and flags. But these features influenced cartographic production in other regions and were common in early Portuguese cartography.⁷ In Gaffarel's case the exclusion of a comparative study with later charts led to reliance on circumstantial details, and to the ultimate inexactitude of his conclusions.⁸

Contrary to earlier scholars, later authors such as Wagner, Cortesão, Teixeira da Mota and Pinheiro Marques, considered the chart to be a product of Portuguese cartography, dating to around 1500. Concerning the date, the most evident argument is the presence of a flag with symbols associated with the Spanish Catholic monarchs, Fernando and Isabel, in Granada, which means that the chart was made after 1492. As to the hypothesized Portuguese origins, their conclusions were mostly based on the presence of many place names showing Portuguese spellings. Other aspects, such as the style of the wind roses, were also mentioned to claim that this chart was a product of early Portuguese cartography.⁹

⁷ In fact, this does not completely exclude other origins, because it was common among cartographers to use decorative elements from different sources. Alfredo Pinheiro Marques wrote: "As for the proximity of the decorative elements to those of the Catalan/Majorcan models, we know that this was common in the earliest Portuguese charts." (Marques, 1987, p. 84).

⁸ A significant example was his opinion that the chart had to be made before 1429 because of the presence of the papal flag in the city of Avignon. Yet, later charts, such as the portulan by Jorge de Aguiar, made in 1492, still portray the same flag.

⁹ See for example (Winter, 1950, p. 39).

Following this interpretation, the chart was included in the well-known *Portugalia Monumenta Cartographica* (hereafter *PMC*). There is a brief reference to it in the very last note of Volume V, where the authors suggested a possible connection between this and two other charts, an anonymous fragment of a portolan chart kept in the ANTT and the famous chart known as Kunstmann III:

A simple perusal of Gaffarel's reproduction shows, however, that the chart is undoubtedly Portuguese; it may have been drawn by the same anonymous cartographer who drew the late xv-century chart of which a fragment is preserved in the Torre do Tombo (Vol. I, p. 5, Plate 3). There are some affinities with the so-called Kunstmann III chart of c. 1506 (Vol. I, pp. 15-6, Plate 6), which might suggest a common authorship. As we cannot deal with this interesting subject here in the detail it deserves, we intend to do so in the near future in a small monograph to be published by the Agrupamento de Estudos de Cartografia Antiga. (Cortêsão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. V, p. 187)

As far as I know, neither Cortêsão nor Teixeira da Mota published the promised monograph. Later, an extended report about the chart was published in the sixth volume (*Supplement*) of the *PMC* (Marques, 1987, pp. 83-86). Besides clarifying Santarém's and Gaffarel's interpretations, the text by Pinheiro Marques included his own contributions and referred to an interesting study by Isabelle Raynaud-Nguyen with inferences about the date of the chart (Du Jourdin, de La Ronciere, Azard, Raynaud-Nguyen & Vannereau, 1984, pp. 217-218). Both these researchers agreed with the Portuguese origin but were reticent about the identity of its author. Regarding the date of production of the chart, Raynaud-Nguyen hypothesized its completion in 1510 based on the presence of sword-shaped crosses in some locations in North Africa:

In Morocco they appear next to the fortress of Ceuta (Cepta) and to the west of huxemas (Alhucemas); then at Oram (Oran), where the place name has been superimposed in larger script on another, which has been deliberately effaced and of which only the initial ma (Mers El Kebir?) remains. A few miles to the east, a third sword indicates Monte Sines, near Ténès. The last sword is close to the fortress of Bougie at the entrance to the gulf of the same name (G. de Bugea). This could be a symbolic representation the points on the North African coast conquered by Spain in the aftermath of the siege of Granada, between 1497 and 1510. (Du Jourdin et al., 1984, p. 217)

Figure 2 - Detail of North Africa in the Dijon Chart. From left to right, the blue rectangles indicate the red crosses shaped like swords approximately in Peñón de Velez, Oran, Monte

Sines and Bougie, according to Isabelle Raynaud-Nguyen. See: Michel Mollat Du Jourdin et al. (1984).

Hence, the sword-shaped crosses represent the results of Pedro Navarro's campaigns - Peñón de Velez in 1508, Oran in 1509, Bougie in January 1510. Moreover, the absence of the crosses in Tripoli, a city captured in July 1510, could indicate that the chart was constructed between January and July 1510.

These are strong arguments but, in my opinion, not conclusive. Before commenting on this point, a detail must be clarified regarding Raynaud-Nguyen's description of the crosses. The first note goes to the cross near Oran. A closer inspection of the pictures seems to confirm that two place names were erased, and the word Oran was written on top. It seems that the two erased names were Oran itself and Mazalquivir (Mers El Kebir), which was conquered in 1505.¹⁰ Nevertheless, the cross seems to point to the place where Oran was first written, which may confirm the idea that the crosses are related to Pedro Navarro's campaigns. It is also significant to note that while Raynaud-Nguyen described four crosses in North Africa a close look at the environs of Bougie revealed a different sort of "cross." In fact, the "cross" above Bougie not only differs from the other crosses but resembles a human figure (see Figure 4). A analogous conclusion could be made about the straight line in Monte Sines that, in reality, does not seem to show the same shape of the crosses in the vicinities of Alhucemas and Oran.

Figure 3 - Detail of the cross near Oran on the Dijon Chart. Note the red cross drawn very close to a Muslim flag with a crescent moon. This image has been rotated 180°, therefore showing the south on top and the north in the bottom.

¹⁰ The ink in the Dijon chart is very faded in that area, nevertheless, by comparing it with the place names in the K3, it is possible to discern that Mazalquivir and Oran are both in red. More about the examination of the toponymy will be presented bellow.

Figure 4 - Detail on the Dijon Chart of the drawing in Bougie that resembles a human figure. This image has been rotated 180°, therefore showing the south on top and the north in the bottom.

As far as I know, no other chart of the period presents sword-shaped crosses in the referred area. However, there are other charts from the late 15th century/early 16th century that show Spanish flags in the referred areas in North Africa.¹¹ According to Tony Campbell (1987) the attribution of dates for the construction of charts based on the presence or absence of flags and heraldry must be cautious:

There are countless instances in the extensive literature where an unsigned chart has been given a definite terminus ad quem on the grounds that it omits any reference to a change that took place in that particular year or because it displays a flag that was superseded at that time. Yet no methodical check was made to see whether dated charts were accurate in that respect. (Campbell, 1987, p. 399)

The same author calls attention to some caveats to this principle, but he also underlines the fact that, in the case of other Christian takeovers in North Africa, cartographers were fast to react and represent those events in their charts:

On the other hand, the rapidity with which the capture of Ceuta was generally acknowledged gives some justification for treating the earlier Arab insignia as a terminus ad quem of 1415. In the same way, the Spanish flag seems to have been speedily inserted over Granada after 1492 and beside Oran, Bougie (Bejaia), and Tripoli in Libya after those towns were subdued in 1509-10. If the presence of these flags has caused some charts to be moved out of the fifteenth century, their absence provides reasonable (though inconclusive) grounds for a date before 1510. (Campbell, 1987, p. 401)

Hence, there is a possibility that the crosses were added after the chart was already finished, by someone (perhaps the chart's owner) attempting to signal the Spanish conquests. This

¹¹ For example, the anonymous chart (attributed to Pedro Reinel) at the Bayerrische Staatsbibliothek, Cod. Icon. 140 (chart n°82), (Cortese & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. I, pp. 23-24). Other charts present Spanish flags in the same locations in North Africa, for example, a chart by Salvator de Pilestrina (made in 1533) kept in Toledo, Biblioteca de Castilla-La Mancha, Ms. 530.

hypothesis is reinforced by the uncommonly close placement of a cross to a Muslim flag in the vicinity of Oran, as if to signal a change in geographical influence that had occurred after the chart was finished.

Nevertheless, the lack of a cross in Tripoli may still confirm that all the crosses (and consequently the chart) were drawn before July 1510.¹² Furthermore, all these aspects combined could move the moment of production of the chart to an earlier date, i.e. before 1508.¹³

Anonymous Fragment at Torre do Tombo

The ANTT fragment was described by Cortesão & Teixeira da Mota (1960).¹⁴ This square-shaped parchment of about 28x29 cm, previously used as the cover of a binding or of a parcel of documents, shows the western part of the Mediterranean, including part of the Adriatic, a small portion of the Atlantic off the coast of France and almost all the Gulf of Biscay. It is cut off beyond the west coast of the Iberian Peninsula, half of Italy to east, central and northern England, it shows just half of Sicily and a portion of the coast of Argelia and Tunisia. impossible

A visual comparison of the Dijon and the ANTT fragment identifies many similarities: the positioning, handwriting and spelling of place names is analogous, and the coastlines frequently resembles one another. Genoa is portrayed in all its splendour, when compared to a smaller Venice; the images of the city of Avignon are also very similar in terms of the aspect of the city walls and the depicted flags; the same flag of the Spanish Catholic monarchs appears in the recently conquered city of Granada.

In North Africa, the ANTT fragment only shows the coast between Sillef (Wādī Shalaf, that is, Chelif River, in Algeria) and, to the east, Faches (Sfaqis, in Tunisia). The area near Oran, where the crosses are drawn in the Dijon chart, was cut off from the ANTT fragment, making it impossible to identify any possible representation of those elements. The remaining portion of the coast in North Africa includes Monte Sines and Bougie, but unlike the Dijon chart, the ANTT fragment has no sign of crosses and of the fortress near Bougie. Therefore, if we agree with Raynaud-Nguyen's proposal, and if we remember that the conquered places in North Africa remained under Spanish rule for many years afterwards (for example, this was the case of Bougie from 1510 to 1555), we may well consider that the ANTT fragment is part of a chart produced before 1508-1510, the alleged date for the chart of Dijon. On the other hand, if we assume that the crosses in the Dijon chart were drawn after its completion, for example by an

¹² Although not improbable, the possibility that an eventual cross in Tripoli could have faded and disappeared along the years is remote. This is not evident with a visual inspection and could eventually be confirmed with the use of non-invasive physical or chemical techniques.

¹³ Another remote but not impossible hypothesis may point to yet another conclusions. If we assume that the drawings in Monte Sines and Bougie are not crosses, then we will only be left with the crosses next to Peñón de Velez and Oran. Coincidentally, these were some of the remaining possessions of Spain after 1564, the time when the Peñón was recovered after being lost around 1522.

¹⁴ (Cortesão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. I, p. 5). Another reference can be found in (Cortesão, 1971, p. 218).

owner, conclusions concerning the date of production of the chart at the ANTT are difficult to obtain.

Figure 5 - The anonymous fragment of a portulan chart showing the western Mediterranean, including part of the Adriatic, a small portion of the Atlantic off the coast of France and almost all the Gulf of Biscay. Lisbon, ANTT, Fragmentos, cx. 20, n.º 7.

Figure 6 - Detail of the ANTT fragment showing no sign of crosses and of the fortress in the vicinity of Bougie, North Africa. It covers approximately the coastal stretch from the Gulf of Stora to Titellis (Ra's Tedlès). This image has been rotated 90° counterclockwise, therefore showing the east on top and the west in the bottom.

Nevertheless, the ANTT fragment shows flags and heraldry not present in the Dijon chart, such as the escutcheon of the Spanish Catholic monarchs in Sardinia and one on what is left of Sicily

(the chart was mutilated in that area).¹⁵ In fact, the heraldry and flags associated with the Spanish monarchs are clearer in the ANTT fragment and it is possible to notice the stripes of Aragon, representing King Fernando's coat of arms, and what seems like the two eagles of St. John, used in Queen Isabel's coat of arms. Another difference between the Dijon chart and ANTT fragment is the lack of waterways in the ANTT fragment.

Only one wind rose design is identifiable in the ANTT fragment, and it shows the same pattern as the type B drawn in the Dijon chart:

Figure 7 - Detail of wind roses (type B) from the Dijon chart (left side) and from the ANTT fragment (right side). Note the identical drawings of the eight principal cardinal directions, and specially the illustration of the north cardinal point.

All this evidence points to the strong possibility of both charts having been produced using a common model, that is, we may be in the presence of a common author, a common workshop or, to say the least, the use of common data.

The Kunstmann III Chart

The chart known as Kunstmann III displays Europe, West Africa, the Mediterranean, the Black Sea and the Atlantic with Newfoundland, Greenland and the Brazilian coast. It was drawn on a parchment of about 87x117 cm in several stages from the year 1501 until sometime after 1505.¹⁶ The original was lost from the German archives during World War II. Nevertheless, present day researchers have at their disposal a photograph from the original and the coloured copy made by Otto Progel in 1836.¹⁷

¹⁵ The returning of Sardinia to King Fernando occurred in 1493 and re-established the Kingdom of Naples.

¹⁶ Discussion about these dates of production can be found in (McIntosh & Gaspar, manuscript in preparation).

¹⁷ There is also a photographic reproduction in (Cortêsão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. I, Plate 6).

Figure 8 - Copy of the K3 chart by Otto Progel (1843). Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département Cartes et Plans, CPL GE B-1120 (RES). (Source gallica.bnf.fr / BnF)

The K3 has a latitude scale drawn in the western Atlantic Ocean in the Northern Hemisphere, starting at the Equator and up to 68 degrees north in Greenland. The K3 is probably the earliest known chart in which the locations of places were determined by astronomical observations, that is, latitude readings, in detail those on the west coast of Africa north of the Equator.

The K3 has a was drawn in a slightly bigger parchment than the Dijon chart and its represented geographical area is much larger. There are many observable differences between these two charts in their common area (limited to the Mediterranean basin and Macaronesia, without Cape Verde): the K3 shows much less heraldry and symbols (flags, for example, are completely absent); there are many hydrographic variances (for example, the drawings of the Red Sea are very different); and the representation of Scandinavia also shows variances.

Turning to the “affinities” between the charts, it is evident that some graphic elements, such as the wind roses and, to some extent, the style of the league scale bar over the equator, are very similar.¹⁸ There are also many likenesses in the handwriting and spelling but these await a closer look in the future.

¹⁸ “There are some affinities with the so-called Kunstmann III chart of c. 1506 (Vol. I, pp. 15-6, Plate 6), which might suggest a common authorship.” (Cortêsão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. V, p. 187).

Figure 9 - Detail of a wind rose with the fleur-de-lys from the K3 copy by Progel (left side) and of a wind rose with the fleur-de-lys from the Dijon chart (right side). Notice the similarities to the wind roses in Figure 7.

Figure 10 - Detail of a wind rose with the fleur-de-lys from the K3 copy by Progel (left side) and of a wind rose with the fleur-de-lys from the Dijon chart (right side).

More about the affinities between the three charts were investigated via a comparative study of the toponomy of a common area to the charts and via cartometric methods to access their implicit geometry. Results will be shown in the next sections.

Comparative Toponomy

In this study, the toponomy of the ANTT fragment, K3, and Dijon chart have been compared with that of another cartographic object, in this case, the Cantino planisphere, made in 1502.¹⁹ While the results of the comparison are promising, the study was affected by some practical

¹⁹ The Cantino Planisphere, was chosen for practical reasons. It is probably the most relevant product of early Portuguese cartography and was used as a source of information for subsequent charts. It displays the world known at the time and was drawn in three parchment leaves measuring overall 105x220 cm. Although it is a planisphere, the area of the Mediterranean, used data from portolan sources.

restrictions.²⁰ Due to the deterioration of the ink of the Dijon chart in several zones and the fragmentary nature of the ANTT chart, a choice was made of limiting the survey of toponyms to the coast between Marseille and Rome. Another obvious aspect to underline is that the comparison was made just among the three charts and the Cantino planisphere and not with the full universe of extant charts of the period (let us assume 1500 to 1520).

A list of names for the area is provided below:

ANTT fragment	Dijon chart	K3	Cantino
marselha	marselha	marselha	marselha
iaire (?) ²¹	Ile Maire (?)	Ile Maire (?)	iaire (?)
aquilles	aquilles	-	aquilles
			Sasigni (?)
toron	-	-	tollon
-	?	-	-
terra (?)	-	-	-
eres	-	-	-
- ²²	ilhas eres?	Ilhas deres	Ilhas de Rex
bergancon	bergancon	bergancon	borganso
frezull (?)	frezull (?)	-	frezull
furna	-	-	-
Sta margarita	Sta margarita	Sta margarida	-
nica	-	nica	-
villafranca	villafranca	villa franca	villa franca
monego	monego	monego	monego
p. moris	p. moris	p. maris	p. morixe (?)
tara	tara (?)	-	-
cabo dreimeire (?)	cabo dreimeire	c. dreimeire (?)	-
arbenga	arbenga	arbenga	arbenga
finá	final	-	finall
nori	-	nori (?)	-
?	-	-	-
Sao(na)	Saona	saona	Saona
S. p (?)	S. (?)	-	Sam.p (?) ²³

²⁰ Paul Gaffarel made a list of place names for the Dijon chart, see (Gaffarel, 1874, pp. 168-199). The list is useful, but it includes some mistakes. (McIntosh & Gaspar, 2018) presents a survey of the toponymy of Brazil, Africa, Newfoundland, Baltic and Scandinavia. As far as I know, nothing has been published before now about the toponymy of the ANTT fragment.

²¹ Possibly modern Ile Maire.

²² In the ANTT fragment the name of Îles d'Hyères (Ilhas deres) is written offshore and the place name *eres* (Hyères) is written inland. The opposite happens in both the Dijon chart and the K3 where *Ilhas deres* are written inland.

²³ Probably Sampierdarena.

Jan(oa)	ianoa	ianoa	Ienova
-	-	reco	-
camo(gie)	camogi	camogi (?)	camogi
p. fino	p. fini	-	porto fini
capa(llo)	capallo	capallo	-
chiavari (?)	-	-	-
levanto	levanto	-	-
p. vener (?)	p. vener (?)	p. venert	porto veneri (?)
a speza	speza	a speza	A speza
o crovo (?)	crovo (?)	-	crovo (?)
a magra	a magra	a magra	a magra
lavenca	lavenca (?)	lavenca	Lavenca
motrom	motrom (?)	motrõ	motroni (?)
-	-	-	larno
pisa	pisa	pisa	pissa
p. pisano	p. pisano	p. pisano	p. varsiano (?)
-	monte negro (?)	-	-
porto barato	p. barato	p. barato	p. barato
pionbino	piobino	pionbin	pionbino
			frevi (?)
p. ercoll (?)	-	-	-
a troia	a troia	a troia	a troya
castilhon	castilhon	-	castilloni
talamom	talamon	tolomon	-
-	-	-	Sto estevan
-	-	-	cerceli (?)
-	-	-	ancona ²⁴
mon. argental	m. argental	m. argental	-
p. ercoli	p. ercoli (?)	-	-
monte alto (?)	-	-	-
corneto	corneto	corneto	corneto
civita velha	civita velha	civita (?)	civita velha
cabo linara	c. de linar	c. de linar	c. de linar
Santa Severa	S. Severa	-	-
Roma	Roma	Roma	Roma

Table 1 - Toponymy for the coasts between Marseille and Rome. (?) count for inferred place names; (-) count for no correspondance.

²⁴ The occurrence of Ancona in the west coast of Italy is most probably a copy mistake. As far as I know, this only happened in another chart, that is, the anonymous chart (probably by Pedro Reinel) at the Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Cod. Icon. 140 (chart n°82), (Cortesão & Teixeira da Mota, 1960, Vol. I, pp. 23-24).

For the considered area, the ANTT fragment shows 50 place names, the Dijon chart 43, and the K3 shows 33 (the Cantino planisphere shows 39 place names). Looking at the red ink place names in the list, noteworthy correspondences between the three charts emerge. Firstly, there is a similar percentage of red names in the considered area (TT 30%, Dijon 26%, K3 30%, Cantino 28%, of the total place names). Secondly, with minor differences, the TT, Dijon and K3 share the same red names (that did not occur in 4 out of 14 occurrences).²⁵ Even though the Mediterranean area in the K3 was smaller than the same area in the Dijon chart and the ANTT fragment, a similar percentage and correspondences of red names occurs. This may raise a question concerning the process of assigning toponyms to these specific charts: is it possible that the artisans responsible for writing place names distributed first red names and then filled the empty space with the available black ink names?²⁶

Regarding the spelling of place names, many similarities occur, as seen in Table 1. Another noteworthy occurrence observed in this survey was that two specific toponyms, that is, Villa Franca and Porto Pisano, appear written in red ink in the three charts (in the Cantino only Villa Franca is written in red). According to Tony Campbell's survey of red ink place names, this match was recorded for the first time in a Majorcan chart produced by Pietro Russo in 1508.²⁷ For the moment, there is no formal intention of establishing a direct link with the work of Russo, but just to highlight another argument in favour of a correlation between the Dijon chart, the ANTT fragment and the K3 that can be further investigated in the future.²⁸

So far, for the coast between Marseille and Rome, it seems that the same list of place names was used to produce the ANTT fragment and the Dijon chart. With some caution, the same preliminary conclusion can be advanced for the K3. A cursory inspection of place names for other coastal regions on the Dijon chart, ANTT fragment and K3 demonstrated the same pattern of congruence reported above. To definitively address the relationship between the toponyms on these three charts, however, an expanded analysis will be required.

²⁵ Progel's coloured copy of the K3 was used to determine red ink place names.

²⁶ This procedure was advanced in (Cortés, 1551), fl. lxxiii r: "y primeramente se han de escribir de colorado los puertos y cabos principales, y famosas ciudades, y otras cosas notables: y todo lo demás de negro. (...)". Translation: "and first write in color the principal ports and capes, and other notable features: and everything else in black", please note: the translation is mine. (McIntosh, 2013, pp. 27–28), supports this procedure. Nevertheless, Ramón Pujades is more inclined to the opposite procedure, that is, he states that black names were written first, (Pujades, 2007, p. 480–481). For example, the already mentioned anonymous chart at Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Cod. Icon. 140 (chart nº82), only shows black place names and the spaces for the red place names are empty.

²⁷ See (Campbell, 2014).

²⁸ If the date of production of the K3, as suggested in (McIntosh & Gaspar, 2018), i.e. 1501–1506, is to be accepted, then the K3 must count as the first chart to have both Villa Franca and Porto Pisano in red.

Cartometric Analysis: Dijon Chart

The internal geometry of the three charts was inspected using the program MapAnalyst, but, in this paper, only the results for the Dijon chart will be shown.²⁹ In a few words, the program compared the Dijon chart with a modern representation of the Earth, in this case, an image of the surface in a cylindrical projection centered at the equator. A total of 194 control points was used to establish a correspondence between the coordinates of selected locations in the modern map and the same locations in the old chart. Then, the program generated a grid of parallels and meridians for the Dijon chart, as they would appear if we linked the points of the same latitude and longitude. That grid shows distortions that reveal information about the geometrical features of the chart (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Resulting distorted grid for the Dijon chart displaying the 194 control points (from MapAnalyst).

The pattern of the grid does not reveal major divergences from others generated from different portolan charts of the period.³⁰ Some of those common aspects are the usual counterclockwise tilt of the Gibraltar-Iskenderun axis, and the anomalies in the scale in some zones: the typical

²⁹ The internal geometry of portolan charts is associated with the representation of the actual geographic features (coastlines, islands, etc.) and reflect the navigational techniques used to acquire the geographical information. See (Gaspar & Leitão, 2018).

³⁰ For examples of analogous grids from charts of the period see (Gaspar, 2010), (Gaspar, 2012), (Dias, 2018). Recently, a systematic survey of the geometry of early charts has been conducted within the MEDEA-CHART project. More results of this investigation are expected to be published in the near future.

aberrations (elbow) in the Aegean Sea, the distortion in the Gulf of Sirte, and the distortion in the Black Sea, indicating a larger scale, when compared to the Mediterranean Sea.

The plotting of the errors of the latitude against longitude further links the Dijon chart to other portolan charts of the period, which present analogous error distributions.³¹ The following graphic was obtained for the errors of the latitudes after correcting the tilt of the Gibraltar-Iskenderun axis (in this case the rotation of the Mediterranean, when we set the origin in Gibraltar, was around 7° ACW, in relation to the parallel of 36°).

Graphic 1 - Distribution of the Errors of Latitude against Longitude plot, (with tilt correction) for the Dijon chart.

It is possible to observe three major clusters: 1) the Atlantic coast of Europe, that intersects the Mediterranean west of Italy (orange), from around 30° West to 4° West; 2) the western Mediterranean, Adriatic and Central Mediterranean, from around 4° West to 24° East; and 3) the Aegean, Levant and Black Sea, from around 24° East to 41° East.

In the case of the Dijon chart, the dispersion of the errors of the latitude of the Islands of the Azores, Madeira and Canaries and of West coast of Africa grow with the longitude, towards the west. This occurs because, probably, the values of the latitude used to plot those places were determined using the “normal” methods for navigation in the Mediterranean. That is, using uncorrected magnetic directions and distances, and not by using systematic astronomical observations. It is also worth noting that the dispersion of values for the eastern part of the

³¹ See, for example, (Dias, 2018).

Mediterranean (Black Sea, Levant, and to some degree, the Aegean and Central Mediterranean) is smaller than in earlier charts, which may suggest an improvement of the data used to plot that area over time.

Presently, the reasons behind these patterns of errors are still under investigation. One of the strongest hypotheses is the spatial distribution of the magnetic declination affecting the Mediterranean, as shown by recent research based in the theoretical model CALS7K (Korte and Constable 2005).³² The characteristics of the sea routes as well as the influence of local geophysical and meteorological features are also valid causes that should be further investigated in the future.

Cartometric Analysis: Comparing the Resulting Grids of the Dijon Chart, ANTT Fragment and K3.

Of special interest is the comparison of the grid obtained using MapAnalyst for the Dijon chart and the other two charts, that is, the ANTT fragment and the K3. In theory, if the location and relative distances of the places on the three charts corresponded, an undistorted square grid would be obtained for both the ANTT fragment and K3. In this case, the Dijon chart was used as the reference model against which the remaining charts were compared.³³

Figure 12 - Image of the grid resulting from a comparison of the **K3** to the Dijon chart.

³² For more on the influence of magnetic declination in the geometry of portulan charts see (Gaspar, 2010) and (Gaspar, 2008).

³³ In the MapAnalyst application, the Dijon chart was used as the “new map” and the ANTT fragment and K3 were used as the “old map”.

For the ANTT fragment, although not a perfect match, the result was meaningful to this study because it showed a relatively precise fit of the grids of both charts (note that the inclination of the ANTT fragment grid was not corrected). This finding lends even more weight to the hypothesis, suggested by the charts' graphic similarities, that the Dijon and ANTT fragment were made using a common data set.

Repeating the process for the Dijon and K3, the following grid for the Mediterranean was obtained:

Figure 13 - Image of the resulting grid of the K3, when compared to the Dijon chart. A crop of of the photographic reproduction (artotype) of the original, Stevenson (1903), no. 3, was used here.

In this case, notice that the matching of the two grids to each other is poorer than that obtained for the previous comparison between the ANTT fragment and the Dijon chart. Naturally, the area of the Mediterranean in the K3 is smaller than in the Dijon chart, but still no major unexpected aberrations are seen. Hence, if a common data set was used, we can assume that the reduction of scale was well performed. The fitting obtain in this comparison may point to similar pattern of errors, as seen in Graphic 1, which may be confirmed in future analysis.

Concluding Remarks

This paper addressed questions left unanswered by previous researchers concerning three Portuguese charts from the beginning of the 16th century, namely the portolan chart at the

Bibliothèque Municipale of Dijon, a fragment of a chart kept in Lisbon in the Archive at Torre do Tombo, and the chart known as Kunstmann III. That was the point of departure for a broader study of those charts using a multi-analytic approach encompassing traditional and digital research techniques.

For practical reasons previously explained, the Dijon chart was the point of reference used to explore correlations with other two early Portuguese nautical charts. The use of cartometric methods reinforced some of the ideas of earlier researchers and yielded some new information about the charts. The internal geometry of the Dijon chart was studied for the first time using MapAnalyst and the errors of latitude were shown. Using the same program, it was shown that with a high degree of confidence, the ANTT fragment and the Dijon chart share a common data set. The investigation into the charts' toponymy strongly indicates that the three charts may have drawn on a common list of place names.

Regarding the suggestion of the *PMC* about "some affinities of the Dijon chart with the Kunstmann III", some advancement was made. It was highlighted that the wind roses have the same pattern, that there are similarities in the distribution of red ink names, and that there is a fitting of the internal geometries of the Dijon chart and the K3 (which may also indicate resemblances in the distribution of the errors of the coordinates). to now, the hypothesis of a common author of the charts can only be used to motivate further analysis.

Finally, the results obtained confirm that the followed methodology, that is, a multi-analytic approach encompassing traditional and digital research techniques, present a powerful set of tools that should be amply integrated into the present and future research in the history of cartography.

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